

**Tribhuvan University
Institute of Science and Technology**

**A PROJECT REPORT
on
ONLINE CARD GAME – BRAY**

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the bachelor's degree in information technology.

**Submitted by:
Sagar Kumar Thakur (BIT 332/077)**

**Submitted to:
Department of Science and Technology,
Mahendra Morang Adarsh Multiple Campus, Biratnagar**

February, 2025

Tribhuvan University
Institute of Science and Technology

SUPERVISOR'S RECOMMENDATION

I hereby recommended that this project prepared under my supervision by **Sagar Kumar Thakur** entitled “**Online Card Game – BRAY**” in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the bachelor’s degree in information technology be processed for further evaluation.

Signature

Mr. Ujjwal Rijal

Supervisor

Mahendra Morang Aadarsh Multiple Campus

Department of Science and Technology

Tribhuvan University
Institute of Science and Technology

LETTER OF APPROVAL

This is to certify that this project prepared by **SAGAR KUMAR THAKUR** entitled “**ONLINE CARD GAME – BRAY**” in partial fulfilment of the requirements for bachelor’s degree in information technology has been evaluated. In our opinion, it is satisfactory in the scope and quality as a project for the required degree.

SIGNATURE of Supervisor

SIGNATURE of Coordinator

Mr. Ujjwal Rijal
MMAM Campus,
Biratnagar, Morang

Dr. Shashit Kumar Yadav
MMAM Campus,
Biratnagar, Morang

SIGNATURE of Internal Examiner

SIGNATURE of External Examiner

Name:

Name:

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, I would like to thank the God for giving me opportunity to complete and submit the final year project. Without their blessings, this accomplishment would not have been possible.

Secondly, I extend my sincere thanks to my parents for their constant support, encouragement, and love throughout this journey. Their unwavering belief in me has been a source of motivation and strength during challenging times.

I would also like to express my profound appreciation to my project supervisor, Mr. Ujjwal Rijal, whose invaluable guidance, expertise, and feedback were crucial in shaping this project. Your patience and insights have been greatly appreciated.

In addition, I am grateful to Mahendra Morang Adarsh Multiple Campus, Tribhuvan University, and respected teachers for providing the necessary resources and environment for my project.

Lastly, I would like to thank my friends, classmates, and anyone who contributed, directly or indirectly, to the success of this project.

Sagar Kumar Thakur

February, 2025

ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of digital gaming has opened new opportunities for traditional card games to evolve into engaging online experiences. This project focuses on developing "Online Card Game - Bray," a multiplayer card game aimed at providing an immersive and strategic gaming environment. The game incorporates unique scoring mechanics and rules, emphasizing player decision-making and strategic thinking. Developed using Unity and Photon Unity Networking (PUN2), "Online Card Game - Bray" supports seamless multiplayer interactions with a focus on user-friendly design and responsiveness across devices. The project aims to enhance gameplay by introducing features such as dynamic card arrangements, smooth animations, and adaptive UI layouts. Additionally, the game provides a data collection mechanism to facilitate the future integration of machine learning-based bots, enabling intelligent gameplay even with fewer players. By blending traditional card game rules with modern technology, "Online Card Game - Bray" strives to create a versatile and globally accessible gaming platform, thereby expanding the reach and appeal of card games in the digital era.

Keywords: decision-making, strategic thinking, Unity, Photon Unity Networking, card game.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SUPERVISOR’S RECOMMENDATION.....	ii
LETTER OF APPROVAL	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iv
ABSTRACT.....	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vi
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
LIST OF TABLES	ix
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	x
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. Game Overview	1
1.2. Problem Statement.....	1
1.3. Objectives	1
1.4. Scope and Limitations.....	2
1.4.1. Scope.....	2
1.4.2. Limitations	3
1.5. Report Organization.....	3
CHAPTER 2: BACKGROUND STUDY AND LITERATURE REVIEW.....	5
2.1. Background Study.....	5
2.1.1. Fundamental Theories.....	5
2.1.2. General Concepts	5
2.1.3. Terminologies.....	6
2.2. Literature Review.....	7
CHAPTER 3: SYSTEM ANALYSIS	9
3.1. Requirement Analysis	9
3.1.1. Functional Requirements	9
3.1.2. Non-Functional Requirements	10
3.2. Feasibility Study	11
3.2.1 Technical feasibility	11
3.2.2 Operational feasibility.....	11
3.2.3 Economic feasibility	12
3.2.4 Schedule feasibility.....	12
3.3 Analysis.....	13

3.3.1. Object Modelling	13
3.3.2. Dynamic Modelling	15
3.3.3 Process Modelling.....	18
CHAPTER 4: SYSTEM DESIGN.....	19
4.1. Design	19
4.1.1. Class Diagram.....	19
4.1.2 State Diagram.....	26
4.1.3. Sequence Diagram	28
4.1.4. Component Diagram.....	31
4.1.5. Deployment Diagram.....	32
4.2. Algorithm Details.....	33
CHAPTER 5: IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING	37
5.1. IMPLEMENTATION.....	37
5.1.1. Tools Used.....	37
5.1.2. Implementation Details of Modules.....	38
5.2. Testing.....	39
5.2.1. Test Cases for Unit Testing	39
5.3. Result Analysis.....	45
CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS	46
6.1. Conclusion	46
6.2. Future Recommendations	46
REFERENCES	48
APPENDICES	49

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Use Case Diagram	10
Figure 2: Class Diagram	14
Figure 3: Object Diagram	15
Figure 4: Initial State Diagram	16
Figure 5: Initial Sequence Diagram	17
Figure 6: Activity Diagram	18
Figure 7: Class Diagram of Photon Manager	19
Figure 8: Class Diagram of Other Players Position	20
Figure 9: Class Diagram of Lobby manager	21
Figure 10: Class Diagram of Pass card	23
Figure 11: Class Diagram of Game Logic and Network Call	25
Figure 12: State Diagram	27
Figure 13: Sequence Diagram	30
Figure 14: Component Diagram	31
Figure 15: Deployment Diagram	33
Figure 16: Initial Screen	49
Figure 17: Waiting State	49
Figure 18: Join Room Screen	50
Figure 19: First Player Screen	50
Figure 20: Second Player Screen	50
Figure 21: Third Player Screen	51
Figure 22: Fourth Player Screen	51
Figure 23: Card Selection for Passing	51
Figure 24: After card exchange First player's screen	52
Figure 25: Card Throwing Turn of Third player	52
Figure 26: Point displayed at top	52

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Gantt Chart.....	13
Table 2: Card Selection Test	40
Table 3: Card Passing Test	40
Table 4: Round Management Test.....	41
Table 5: Points Calculation Text	41
Table 6: Room Creation Test	42
Table 7: Room Joining Test	42
Table 8: UI Update After Card Passing Test	43
Table 9: Card Status Display Test	43
Table 10: Invalid Card Selection Text.....	44
Table 11: Throwing Invalid Card Test	44
Table 12: Throwing Bray Card Test.....	45

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

API	Application Programming Interface
App	Application
BRAY	Queen of Spades
C#	C Sharp
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
PUN	Photon Unity Network
RPC	Remote Procedural Call
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modelling Language

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Game Overview

Card games are popular from centuries, offering players not only entertainment but also opportunities to develop strategic thinking, decision-making and social interaction. Beyond gaming, cards play a significant role in probability, where students can understand concept of probability using cards easily.

As part of the final year project, Online Card Game – BRAY, is a multiplayer card game designed to offer a challenging and engaging experience to players. The game has unique rules, and strategy which combines players interaction with this game. The objective is to avoid accumulating 101 points by winning hands that contains hearts and Queen of spades. The game requires exactly 4 players, the players carefully plan their moves to either minimize or avoid points or strategically force opponents to gain more.

1.2. Problem Statement

Many card games such as Call Break, Marriage, and 29 are widely available on online platforms, allowing players to enjoy the game digitally. However, traditional card games like Bray are gradually disappearing due to lack of digital transformation. Bray, with its point-based system, offers more challenging experience compared to many existing card games, yet it remains inaccessible in the digital world.

Currently digitally available card games are not designed specifically for multiplayer gameplay, limiting the experience for those who wish to compete with real players. Bray addresses this gap by fully developed for multiplayer from the start. Upon its initial launch, the game will allow players to join matches with friends or compete against opponents globally, offering a more competitive and entertaining gameplay experience with real players.

1.3. Objectives

The primary objective of Bray is to develop an online card game that provides a challenging and enjoyable experience for players worldwide. The key objectives are following:

- To implement a unique scoring system that adds complexity in the game.
- To enable multiplayer gameplay which enables players to join and play with opponents worldwide.

- To create a visually appealing and responsive user interface that adapts to different devices.

1.4. Scope and Limitations

1.4.1. Scope

The scope of the Online Card Game – BRAY includes the following key components:

i. Multiplayer Functionality:

The game is designed specifically for multiplayer gameplay, where 4 players can join a game and play in real time. Players can create a room with unique name and invite friends sharing room name to join the game to play as well as they can join any random room to play the game worldwide without room name. Initially the game will launch with only multiplayer experience.

ii. Card Passing and Scoring System:

The game involves a unique point system where players avoid accumulating 101 points, they will lose. Players earn points by collecting certain cards i.e. hearts contain 1 point each and queen of spade contains 12 points. Players also have opportunity to minimize their points by not winning any hand, which is also called honours it minimizes players point by 5 and also, they can minimize 5 points by taking 0 points serially 3 times. Players have also a key advantage to passing 5 cards to the player at right before starting of game which help them to pass cards which can lead to win hand.

iii. User Interface and User Experience:

The project will include a user-friendly interface that is responsive across multiple devices, ensuring that players on desktop and mobile platforms have a seamless experience. The process of connecting on game room creation process and join process will be very easy. The interface will display each players cards, card passing process and clear point visualization.

iv. Game Mechanics and Rule Implementation:

The core mechanics of the Bray, will be fully implemented including card passing process, point calculations, and round progression. The game will also feature mechanism to enforce the rules and ensure fair play during each round.

v. Global Accessibility:

As part of the multiplayer design, the game will support global players, allowing players to connect from different regions and play together. This feature will help to expand the game's reach and engage a broader audience.

The game will not include offline gameplay on initial release, and there will not be any AI-controlled bots or opponents. Future updates may introduce these features based on user feedback and data collected from multiplayer sessions.

1.4.2. Limitations

1. Dependency on Internet Connectivity:

The game is currently designed for online multiplayer mode. Players with unstable or low-speed internet connections may experience disruptions, affecting gameplay quality.

2. Limited Player Customization:

The initial version of the game lacks advanced customization options, such as personalized avatars or customizable game settings, which could enhance user experience.

3. Device-Specific Performance Variations:

Although designed for multiple platforms, differences in screen sizes, resolutions, and hardware capabilities may result in inconsistent experiences across devices.

4. Absence of Advanced Features:

Additional gameplay features, such as tournament modes or detailed performance statistics, are not included in the initial prototype, limiting the game's appeal to competitive players

5. Learning Curve for New Users:

Players who are unfamiliar with the unique rules and scoring system of 'Bray' may find it difficult to adapt, potentially leading to frustration and reduced engagement.

1.5. Report Organization

This report is organized into the following chapters:

Chapter 1: Introduction

Chapter 2: Background Study and Literature Review

Chapter 3: System Analysis

Chapter 4: System Design

Chapter 5: Implementation and Testing

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Future Recommendations

First Chapter provides an overview of the project, including objectives, scope, and significance.

Second Chapter examines existing research, related works, and theoretical foundations relevant to the project.

Third Chapter details the requirements, problem analysis, and overall system workflow.

Fourth Chapter describes the architectural and technical design, including data flow, user interface layouts, and key algorithms.

Fifth Chapter covers the practical development of the system, tools used, coding approaches, and results from testing to validate functionality.

Sixth Chapter summarizes the achievements of the project, addresses its limitations, and suggests potential enhancements for future work.

CHAPTER 2: BACKGROUND STUDY AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Background Study

2.1.1. Fundamental Theories

- **Game Theory:**

Game theory is the study of player interactions and strategic decision-making in cooperative or competitive environment. It looks at how players choose to maximize their outcomes while considering the potential moves of their rivals. Determining the optimal play strategies in card games like as Bray requires a thorough understanding of game theory. Players must evaluate various scenarios, predict their opponents' moves, and adjust their decisions to achieve the best outcomes. Concepts like Nash equilibrium, which describes a stable condition in which no actor can unilaterally change their approach to improve their result, are especially relevant. various rules provide a systematic framework for understanding and enhancing decision-making in various types of games.

- **Networking in Multiplayer Games:**

Networking in multiplayer games refers to creating a seamless link between players so that real-time communication is possible. This is accomplished using architectures such as the client-server model, where a central server manages game data and synchronizes actions across connected clients. Key concerns include ensuring low latency, controlling data consistency, and keeping all players in sync. Tools like Photon Unity Networking (PUN), which provide reliable data transfer, room based matching, and efficient communication protocols, satisfy these requirements. These technologies manage player updates, resolve conflicts during concurrent actions, and ensure a fun and equitable multiplayer gaming experience. Networking 5 is necessary to ensure seamless gameplay across numerous devices and locations.

2.1.2. General Concepts

1. **Card Game Mechanics:**

Card games have common mechanics such as:

1. **Hand Management:** Players manage their cards to achieve specific goals.
2. **Turn-Based Play:** Players make moves sequentially.

3. **Point System:** Scoring depends on specific card combinations or game rules. For Bray, the mechanics include passing cards, avoiding high-value cards, and aiming for "honours" to reduce points.

2. Game Physics and Animation:

Game engines like Unity enable the use of animation technologies to enhance game play by creating visually appealing elements. In particular, the round number in "Online Card Game– BRAY" is animated, providing a dynamic visually appealing indication of game progress. Although more complex animations, such as simulating card movements like shuffling and flipping, can be included, the project's use of simple animations ensure clarity and focuses on improving the player's overall experience without excessive complexity.

3. Player Roles and Views:

The role of each player affects gameplay perspective:

1. **Dynamic UI:** Adjusts to display each player's cards relative to their position, previous thrown card at top, left and right and own thrown card at bottom, shows points of players at top right with respective player's names.

2. **Hidden Information:** Only the players own cards are visible, while others only avatar icon.

4. Circular Card Passing:

Players in "Online Card Game– BRAY" use a clockwise card-passing system to balance games and offer strategic depth. Players carefully select which cards to pass in attempt to improve their hand and predict forthcoming cards. This approach ensures fairness, disrupts opponent planning, and enhances the game's competitive and interactive elements.

2.1.3. Terminologies

- **Photon Unity Networking (PUN):**

Photon Unity Networking (PUN) is a tool used in Unity game development to enable multiplayer functionality. In terms of helping synchronize player actions, game data, and other game features across many devices, it enables real-time communication between players. By offering capabilities like matchmaking, room creation, player synchronization, and networked object management, PUN makes it easier to create multiplayer games and guarantees that players can communicate with one another in a smooth online setting.

- **Card Suit:**

In a deck of playing cards, the suit refers to one of the four categories used to classify the cards: Hearts, Diamonds, Clubs, and Spades. Each suit consists of thirteen cards, including

numbers 2 through 10, and face cards (Jack, Queen, King) along with an Ace. The suit system plays an important role in determining the rank and value of cards in various games, including Bray. The suit often influences strategic decisions, especially when certain cards in specific suits are worth more or have unique rules attached.

- **Honors:**

In Bray, the “Honors” rule adds an additional layer of strategy and decision-making. Players are rewarded or penalized based on their ability to avoid winning hands during the game. If a player successfully refrains from winning any hand in a round, they score negative points, making it a strategic move. However, if a player fails and wins a hand, they incur positive points, along with additional penalties for certain card combinations. The Honors system encourages players to think carefully about their moves, balancing offense and defence to manage their score effectively.

2.2. Literature Review

A review of related literature is a theory that researchers employ to explain why research difficulties arise. It can be found in a variety of books, journals, papers and other material.

Gokhale and Traulsen (2014), discuss the expansion of evolutionary game theory into multiplayer dynamics, focusing on non-linearities inherent in natural systems. Through replicator dynamics, they demonstrate how multiplayer games enable the exploration of complex scenarios, such as social dilemmas, by introducing group benefits that increase less than linearly with the number of cooperators. Their methodology extends findings from classical two-player game theory by incorporating finite population analysis and stochastic effects. The study utilizes polynomial payoff functions to determine equilibrium states and fixation probabilities, validated through simulation and analytical models. Applications in social sciences, ecology, and population genetics highlight the utility of this approach in understanding real-world phenomena like cooperation thresholds and non-Mendelian inheritance patterns. [1]

According to Norozpour and Safaei (2020), provide a comprehensive overview of game theory, emphasizing its historical development and applications. The study introduces fundamental concepts like Nash equilibrium and dominance, alongside mixed strategies and extensive games with both perfect and imperfect information. Additionally, it explores game theory’s role in zero-sum games and auction bidding. The authors highlight the

practical utility of game theory in diverse fields such as economics, biology, and political science. A particular focus is placed on strategic interactions and decision-making processes, demonstrating the theory's ability to model real-world scenarios like oligopolies and market competitions. [2]

Likewise, Kordaki and Gousiou (2017), conducted a systematic review of digital card games (DCGs) as educational tools over a decade (2003–2013). Their findings highlighted the potential of DCGs in fostering engagement and learning across diverse subjects, such as mathematics, languages, computer science, and health education. The study revealed two main uses of DCGs: gameplay, where students learn through playing, and game-construction, where students develop games to learn programming and design concepts. Constructivist and social learning theories, such as active learning and collaboration, formed the pedagogical backbone for many DCGs. The reviewed studies showed that DCGs promote cognitive skills like matching, grouping, and decision-making. Furthermore, the integration of modern technologies, including augmented reality and speech-enriched environments, enhances interactivity and engagement. However, the study also noted gaps, such as the need for comprehensive evaluations of their educational impact. [3]

CHAPTER 3: SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1. Requirement Analysis

Requirement analysis is a critical phase where the functional and non-functional needs of the system are identified to define the overall structure and capabilities of the “Online Card Game BRAY”.

3.1.1. Functional Requirements

Functional Requirements specify the core functionalities the system must deliver to ensure a seamless experience in multiplayer card gameplay. These requirements for “Bray” include:

- **Room Creation and Joining:** Users should be able to create a game room or join an existing one. Each room can accommodate up to four players.
- **Card Dealing and Passing:** At start of each round, each player is dealt 13 cards. Players then select five cards to pass to the player on their right. This function must execute synchronously across all player interface to ensure real-time gameplay consistency.
- **Game Play Mechanism:** Players can throw one card at centre in a turn-based sequence, which is managed by the game’s logic to maintain proper turns and validate moves.
- **Scoring and Rules Enforcement:** The game should automatically calculate scores based on the specific rules of the “Bray”, such as penalties for the queen of spades and point reduction for avoiding hearts. The system should handle these rules consistently, updating each player’s score as the game progress.
- **Display of Player Position:** Cards and player scores should be displayed in specific location based on the player’s position. Each player sees their own cards at the bottom, with other player’s icon displayed clockwise on the screen.

Figure 1: Use Case Diagram

3.1.2. Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements define the system's quality attributes, addressing performance, usability, and scalability aspects.

- **Real-Time Responsiveness:** The game must handle real-time interactions with minimal latency to prevent lag and ensure smooth gameplay, especially during multiplayer actions like card passing and scoring.
- **Usability:** The interface should be intuitive and simple, allowing players to understand game mechanics without extensive instructions. Icons, buttons, and layouts should be clearly visible on both mobile and desktop devices.
- **Reliability and Fault Tolerance:** The game must maintain functionalities even in cases of unexpected disconnections. As in the first version of game doesn't includes reconnection without losing their game state but later it will be added to the game.
- **Scalability:** The game's server should handle multiple active sessions, with the potential to support an increasing number of players and games as the user base grows.

3.2. Feasibility Study

This feasibility study explores the development of “Bray,” an online multiplayer card game with unique rules and mechanics. The study evaluates the technical, operational, economic, and scheduling feasibility of implementing the game and extend global reach via app platforms. The findings suggest that the project is feasible given the available technology, expertise, and resources, although careful planning and execution are required to meet its objectives.

3.2.1 Technical feasibility

The technical feasibility focuses on the tools, technologies, and expertise required for the project.

- **Development Tools:** Unity, in combination with Photon Unity Networking (PUN 2), will be used for game development. Unity’s cross-platform capabilities and robust support for 2D and 2.5D graphics align well with the project’s requirements.
- **Platform Compatibility:** The game will support Android, iOS, and desktop platforms, leveraging Unity’s cross-platform build functionality.
- **Hardware Requirements:** The available hardware, including an NVIDIA RTX 4050 GPU, provides sufficient computational power for development and testing.

3.2.2 Operational feasibility

Operational feasibility examines whether the project aligns with user needs and organizational objectives.

- **User Experience:** Bray’s innovative rules, such as the scoring system and strategic card-passing mechanics, are designed to engage players and enhance decision making skills.
- **Market Demand:** Card games like “Call Break” and “Hearts” have demonstrated strong market potential. Bray’s unique features aim to capture a similar audience while introducing novelty.
- **Skill Availability:** Since this is not a large-scale project, the required skills, such as programming in C# and using the Unity engine for game development, are already possessed by me.

3.2.3 Economic feasibility

Economic feasibility assesses the project's financial viability.

- **Initial Investment:** The primary costs include development tools (Unity subscription), server hosting for multiplayer functionality, and marketing.
- **Revenue Model:** Revenue will be generated through in-app purchases, advertisements, and premium subscriptions.
- **Break-even Analysis:** With efficient marketing and an engaging user experience, the project aims to recover costs within the first year of launch.

3.2.4 Schedule feasibility

The project timeline is divided into five major phases:

1. Requirement Gathering and Analysis

This phase involves identifying and documenting the functional and non-functional requirements of the project. It includes understanding the rules of the card game "Bray," defining gameplay mechanics, and specifying technical needs such as platform compatibility and multiplayer capabilities.

2. Designing

In this phase, the overall architecture and design of the game are developed. Key tasks include creating wireframes for the user interface, designing the game flow, and multiplayer functionality. Unity's development environment will be utilized to prototype basic game elements and establish a clear roadmap for implementation.

3. Coding

The coding phase focuses on implementing the game's functionality based on the designs. This includes programming in C# to develop game mechanics, multiplayer features using Photon Unity Networking (PUN 2). Code optimization and modular development are prioritized to ensure scalability and maintainability.

4. Testing

Comprehensive testing ensures the reliability and performance of the game. This includes functional testing to verify game rules and mechanics, multiplayer testing to ensure synchronization, and stress testing to identify and fix potential issues under high user loads.

5. Implementation and deployment

The final phase involves deploying the game to target platforms, including Android, iOS, and desktop.

Table 1: Gantt Chart

Development Phase	Development Time (in week)											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Planning	█											
Requirement Gathering & Analysis		█	█									
Designing				█	█							
Development						█	█		█	█		
Testing								█			█	
Implementation and Deployment												█
Documentation		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█

3.3 Analysis

3.3.1. Object Modelling

The project is modelled using classes that represent core components of the card game. These include LobbyManager, OtherPlayerPosition, PhotonManger, PassCard, and GameLogicNetworkCall. The relationships and methods within these classes define how objects interact during gameplay.

Class Diagram

Figure 2: Class Diagram

Object Diagram

Figure 3: Object Diagram

3.3.2. Dynamic Modelling

Dynamic modelling describes the interactions and behaviour of objects within the system during the execution of the game. It focuses on how objects change state over time, how they interact with each other, and how the game logic progresses. This type of modelling is

essential for understanding the flow of control and data as the game runs, particularly in multiplayer scenarios.

State Diagram

Figure 4: Initial State Diagram

Sequence Diagram

Figure 5: Initial Sequence Diagram

3.3.3 Process Modelling

Process modelling outlines the sequential flow of activities and tasks within the system during the gameplay. It focuses on the steps involved in executing the game logic, managing player interactions, and ensuring synchronization in multiplayer environments. This type of modelling is crucial for visualizing how processes are triggered, how they progress, and how resources like data and players' actions are managed throughout the game. By breaking down the game processes into manageable components, process modelling helps to analyse and optimize the workflow, ensuring a smooth and coherent gaming experience.

Activity Diagram

Figure 6: Activity Diagram

CHAPTER 4: SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1. Design

Given that the project uses object-oriented programming (OOP), this section emphasizes OOP principles, providing detailed class, object, state, sequence, and activity diagram to clarify system components and their interactions.

4.1.1. Class Diagram

The class diagram define the primary objects in the “Bray” game, including their attributes and methods.

- **Photon Manager**

The PhotonManager class is responsible for managing the connection between the game and the Photon server, enabling multiplayer functionality. It uses Photon.Pun and Photon.Realtime to establish a connection to the Photon network and handle lobby interactions. The class follows the Singleton pattern to ensure there is only one instance of the manager throughout the game session.

Figure 7: Class Diagram of Photon Manager

- **Other Players Position**

The OtherPlayersPosition class uses Unity’s UI system (specifically, the Image component) to represent the avatars of the players. It sets the position and size of the avatars relative to the screen size, ensuring that they appear correctly regardless of the device or screen resolution.

Figure 8: Class Diagram of Other Players Position

- Lobby Manager

The LobbyManager class handles the user interface and interactions related to joining or creating rooms in the lobby for a multiplayer game. It uses Photon.Pun for managing the connection to the Photon server and synchronization across all players. The class provides functionality for players to enter their names, create new rooms, join existing rooms, and display relevant information about the room and game progress. The LobbyManager manages different panels such as the initial panel, room creation panel, room joining panel, and a joined panel, ensuring smooth transitions and proper UI updates. It also handles the back button press logic for navigating between panels. The class ensures that once a player has joined a room, they are ready to begin the game as soon as enough players have joined.

Figure 9: Class Diagram of Lobby manager

- **Pass Card**

The PassCard class is responsible for managing the card-passing mechanic and card playing functionality in a multiplayer card game. It handles the user interactions for selecting, passing, and playing cards during a game session. The class tracks the state of the cards, ensuring players can only select a limited number of cards at a time and follow game rules for playing cards. It uses Photon networking to synchronize actions across all players, allowing for seamless multiplayer gameplay. Additionally, the PassCard class manages transitions between players' turns, ensuring that only the player whose turn it is can make a move. The class also provides methods for handling UI updates, such as showing messages to the player and updating card positions on the screen.

Figure 10: Class Diagram of Pass card

- **Game Logic Network Call**

The `GameLogicNetworkCall` class handles the game logic for a multiplayer card game using Photon Networking in Unity. It manages player interactions, including dealing and displaying cards, handling player names, and updating game states such as rounds and points. The class uses `PhotonView` to synchronize actions across networked players, ensuring that each player's cards and game status are updated in real time. Key features include dealing cards, displaying cards based on player hands, and animating round transitions. The class also includes logic for responsive UI adjustments, card sorting, and player readiness tracking.

Figure 11: Class Diagram of Game Logic and Network Call

4.1.2 State Diagram

A state diagram represents the various states an object in a system can occupy and the transitions between these states. A state diagram can be crafted to reflect the game flow, particularly for the game logic managed by the GameLogicNetworkCall class. Here is a brief description of my project: The state diagram showcases the sequential flow of states within the multiplayer card game environment, ensuring efficient synchronization of game logic across players. The diagram begins with an Idle State, representing the initial stage where players connect to the server and the game waits for the required number of participants. Upon the successful creation of a room and player readiness, the system transitions to the Card Distribution State, where 13 cards are dealt to each player. Following this, the game moves into the Card Passing State, enabling players to select and pass five cards to their neighbouring players as per the rules. Once all players have completed passing, the game enters the Round Execution State, where players sequentially play cards based on game logic, with points being calculated dynamically. If a round is completed without any player exceeding the point threshold, the system transitions to the Next Round State, resetting temporary at tributes and redistributing cards for a new round. Should a player's total score exceed the set limit (i.e., 101 points), the system transitions to the Game End State, where the looser is declared based on the point accumulated. At this point, the diagram concludes by either resetting to the Idle State for a new session or terminating entirely. The state diagram reflects the robustness of the game logic, with clear transitions ensuring that each stage flows smoothly while maintaining synchronization across the network for all participants. This structured flow guarantees a seamless user experience in the multiplayer environment.

Figure 12: State Diagram

4.1.3. Sequence Diagram

A sequence diagram demonstrates the interactions between different entities in the system over time, ensuring a structured flow of actions for the multiplayer card game. This diagram highlights the communication flow between the **Players**, **UI/Client**, **Game Server**, and the **Game Logic** during various game stages, ensuring synchronization for all participants.

1. **Joining the Game:**

- Each **Player** opens the game client and sends a **Join Request** to the **Game Server**.
- The server confirms the join request for each player and displays the game lobby to indicate successful connection.
- This step continues until all four players have successfully joined the game room.

2. **Starting the Game:**

- Once all players are connected, any player clicks **Start Game** to send a **Start Game Request** to the server.
- The **Game Server** initializes the game state, notifies all players that the game has started, and updates the client UI to display the game start confirmation.

3. **Dealing Cards:**

- The **Game Server** deals 13 cards to each player and sends the distributed cards to their respective **Clients**.
- The cards are displayed on the UI for each player to view their current hands.

4. **Passing Cards:**

- Each **Player** selects five cards to pass to the next player.
- The **UI/Client** sends the selected cards to the **Game Server**.
- The **Game Server** validates the passed cards, redistributes them to the correct players, and sends updated hands to all players.

5. **Playing a Round:**

- The game enters a loop where each player takes their turn sequentially.
- Players play a card, and the **Game Server** broadcasts the played card to all players to update their game state.
- This continues until all cards have been played for that round.

6. **Scoring:**

- At the end of each round, the **Game Server** calculates the scores based on game logic.

- Updated scores are sent back to the **UI/Client** for display, ensuring all players see the current standings.

7. **Ending the Game:**

- The **Game Server** checks for a **Lose Condition** (e.g., a player exceeding 101 points).
- If the condition is met, the server announces the **loser**, and the game displays a **Game Over** message.
- If no player has lost, the system transitions to the **Next Round**, resetting temporary attributes and preparing for continued gameplay.

This sequence diagram ensures a structured, synchronized flow between all players and the server, minimizing latency and maintaining a consistent game state for every participant. Each phase, from joining the game to ending it, is handled systematically, enabling smooth progression and real-time feedback throughout the multiplayer experience.

Figure 13: Sequence Diagram

4.1.4. Component Diagram

The component diagram for the **Online Card Game - BRAY** outlines the core modules and their interactions, focusing on a multiplayer card game powered by Photon for real-time synchronization. The client application manages user interactions, game logic, and animations, while the server handles matchmaking and state synchronization. External services, such as authentication and analytics, support seamless gameplay and insightful data tracking. This modular design ensures scalability and efficient performance, tailored for a multiplayer gaming experience.

Figure 14: Component Diagram

4.1.5. Deployment Diagram

A deployment diagram illustrates the structure of a system by showing how software components are distributed across hardware nodes. It provides a clear picture of the physical setup of the system, including how different elements communicate and interact within the environment.

In this game, the deployment diagram represents how various components work together to enable a seamless multiplayer experience.

1. **Player Device:**

- Represents the device used by the player, such as a smartphone or computer.
- Hosts the client application, which includes features like the game interface, game logic, and network management.
- Stores basic player information, such as nicknames, locally using PlayerPrefs.

2. **Photon Server:**

- Provides essential backend services for the game, such as matchmaking, game state management, and real-time data synchronization.
- Ensures that all players remain connected, and game data is updated consistently.

3. **Photon Cloud:**

- Acts as the intermediary, connecting the player devices to the server components.
- Provides reliable and scalable communication channels, ensuring smooth gameplay and real-time interactions.

4. **Communication Flow:**

- The client application connects to the Photon Cloud via the internet.
- The Photon Cloud manages the communication between players and facilitates matchmaking and game state synchronization.

Figure 15: Deployment Diagram

4.2. Algorithm Details

1. Shuffling Algorithm: Fisher-Yates Shuffle

The Fisher-Yates Shuffle is a technique used to randomize the order of a list. Its effectiveness comes from the fact that every permutation of the list is equally probable, which is crucial for fair and unbiased card distribution. The algorithm works by iterating over the list and at each step, swapping the current element with a randomly chosen one from the remaining unprocessed elements. This continues until the entire list has been processed. It is efficient and runs in linear time, making it ideal for shuffling a deck of cards where each game requires fresh randomness.

Algorithm:

Step 1: Start with an array deck of size n , representing the deck of cards.

Step 2: Loop through the array starting from the last index ($n-1$) to the second index (1).

- For each index i :
 1. Generate a random index j such that $0 \leq j \leq i$.
 2. Swap the cards at indices i and j .

Step 3: Continue until all elements are processed.

Step 4: The deck is now shuffled.

2. Card Passing Algorithm: Circular Passing

In card games where players exchange cards in a circular fashion, a simple algorithm ensures the cards flow between players in a predictable pattern. The passing of cards follows a cycle, starting from one player and moving to the next in a fixed sequence. The key to implementing this is using modular arithmetic or circular data structures like arrays or lists, where the position of each player is cyclic. For instance, Player 1 passes cards to Player 2, and when Player 4 has finished, they pass to Player 1, keeping the rotation intact.

Algorithm:

Step 1: Create an array `players[]` representing the players in the game.

Step 2: Create a list of cards[] for each player to hold their hand.

Step 3: For each player, pass 5 cards to the next player in a circular fashion:

- Player 1 gives cards to Player 2.
- Player 2 gives cards to Player 3.
- Player 3 gives cards to Player 4.
- Player 4 gives cards to Player 1.

Step 4: Update the hands of each player accordingly.

3. Scoring System and Point Calculation

The scoring system in a card game involves calculating points based on specific game rules, such as the value of individual cards or sets of cards. In "Bray," for example, points are awarded for specific cards like hearts (1 point each) or the Queen of Spades (12 points). To compute the total score for each player, the algorithm sums up the values of the cards they have accumulated, while also factoring in special conditions such as whether a player "calls honors" and succeeds or fails. This can be modelled as a series of conditional statements that adjust the score according to the rules.

Algorithm:

Step 1: Define the values of specific cards.

Step 2: For each player, sum the values of their collected cards.

Step 3: Factor in special conditions:

- If a player successfully calls "honors", adjust their score.
- If a player fails in their honors call, adjust their score.

Step 4: Output the player's total score.

4. Finite State Machine for Game Flow Management

A Finite State Machine (FSM) is used to control the sequence of events in a game. It breaks down the game into distinct states (such as dealing cards, taking turns, passing cards, and determining the winner) and uses transitions to move from one state to the next based on certain conditions. For example, after dealing the cards, the game transitions to the card passing state, and once cards are passed, the game moves to the next round or to calculating scores. This structured approach ensures that the game progresses logically and predictably.

Algorithm:

Step 1: Define the states of the game.

Step 2: Begin in the "waiting" state.

Step 3: Transition to the next state based on events.

Step 4: After each event, check the game's current state and move to the appropriate next state.

Step 5: Repeat until the game ends.

5. Networking Algorithms: Synchronization for Multiplayer

For multiplayer games, ensuring that all players are seeing the same game state at the same time is crucial. Network synchronization algorithms allow for real-time updates across different players' devices. When a player performs an action, such as passing cards or playing a card, these actions are communicated to the server, which then broadcasts the updated game state to all connected clients. This method ensures that the game state remains consistent across all devices, minimizing latency and preventing desynchronization.

Algorithm:

Step 1: Room Creation:

- When a player creates a room, a unique room identifier is generated.
- Other players can join the room by providing the room identifier.

Step 2: Game State Synchronization:

- Each player's device communicates with the server to send and receive actions (e.g., card plays, moves).
- The server broadcasts the updated game state to all connected players.
- Every client updates their game view based on the new game state.

6. Card Selection and Animation Algorithms

When players select cards in a game, it's important to ensure that the system only accepts valid selections and moves. This can be handled by a selection algorithm, where the system

checks if the card is eligible to be chosen based on the game rules (for example, if it has already been passed). Additionally, animation algorithms are used to handle the smooth movement of cards when they are selected or played, making the experience visually engaging. Techniques like twining or interpolation are often used to create fluid animations for card movements across the screen.

Algorithm:

Step 1: When a player clicks on a card, check if the card can be selected.

Step 2: Once the card is selected, apply an animation:

- Use twining to smoothly move the card from its original position to the new position.

Step 3: Ensure that no other card can be selected while the current card is moving.

CHAPTER 5: IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

5.1. IMPLEMENTATION

During the implementation phase, the planned activities were systematically executed to achieve the project's goals. This stage involved designing, developing, testing, and refining the application to ensure it met the desired requirements. The theoretical framework and conceptual ideas were transformed into a functional product as part of the software development lifecycle.

As the sole developer, I established coding practices, pull request guidelines, and a structured approach to code reviews to maintain code quality and consistency. The project tasks were broken down into smaller, manageable components using user stories, with story points used to estimate the workload and prioritize tasks.

To streamline the implementation process, I utilized various tools and technologies, ensuring that all aspects of development aligned with the project's objectives and standards.

5.1.1. Tools Used

1) **Unity:** Unity is a powerful game development platform that provides an integrated development environment (IDE) for creating interactive 2D and 3D games. Its robust feature set, including a built-in physics engine, scripting support with C#, and a comprehensive asset pipeline, makes it an ideal choice for developing games and simulations across various platforms. Unity also supports a vast library of extensions and assets, enhancing its functionality and flexibility for developers.

2) **Visual Studio:** Visual Studio is a feature-rich integrated development environment (IDE) widely used for software and game development. It provides robust support for various programming languages, including C#, making it an ideal choice for Unity scripting. Visual Studio offers advanced debugging tools, IntelliSense for code completion, and seamless integration with Unity, enabling efficient development workflows. Its extensive library of extensions further enhances functionality, catering to the specific needs of developers across diverse projects.

3) **PlantUML:** PlantUML is an open-source tool used for creating UML diagrams through a simple and concise text-based syntax. It supports a wide range of diagram types, including class diagrams, sequence diagrams, use case diagrams, and more. PlantUML is lightweight and can be integrated into various text editors, IDEs, and build tools, making it highly versatile for developers and architects. Its ability to generate visual representations

directly from text simplifies the process of documenting and communicating complex systems, fostering better collaboration and understanding within teams.

4) Draw.io: Draw.io is a free, open-source diagramming tool widely used for creating a variety of diagrams, including flowcharts, UML diagrams, network diagrams, and more. It offers a user-friendly, drag-and-drop interface with a vast library of shapes, templates, and customization options.

Game UI:

The game UI for my card game, "Bray," is designed to provide a smooth and intuitive player experience. It includes elements like the player's card display, the card passing interface, and visual indicators for the point system. The UI also handles actions like selecting and passing cards, showing game status (e.g., current round, honors), and displaying player scores. By keeping the layout responsive, the UI ensures players can interact with the game efficiently, regardless of the device. The design focuses on simplicity and clarity, allowing players to concentrate on strategy without gratuitous distractions.

Game Scripts and Photon Integration

The C# scripts in the game handle core gameplay mechanics such as card selection, passing, and the point system. These scripts ensure that each player's actions are processed correctly, and the game flow is maintained throughout. Photon is integrated into the game to manage real-time multiplayer interactions, allowing players to connect, synchronize their game states, and interact with each other seamlessly. Together, the game scripts and Photon enable smooth, synchronized gameplays for all players, providing a responsive and interactive experience.

5.1.2. Implementation Details of Modules

1. Game Lobby Module

This module is displayed when players launch the game. In the game lobby, if players open game first time, then, they their nickname input screen will be displayed else players can create or join multiplayer rooms using Photon. The lobby manages the matchmaking process, ensuring players can connect with others to start a round of Bray. Players can select an available room or create a new one, initiating the multiplayer session.

2. Card Selection and Passing Module

Once in a game room, players can interact with the game's main mechanics. This module handles the card selection and passing process. Players can select cards to pass to the next

player and decide which cards to keep. The module ensures that only valid actions occur and updates the game state in real-time for all players using Photon.

3. Game State Management Module

This module is responsible for tracking and managing the game's progress. It includes the round details, player scores, and the overall game flow. The module ensures synchronization of the game state across all players, ensuring that card actions, scores, and game statuses (like points for hearts or the Queen of Spades) are reflected consistently for all players.

4. Player Interaction Module

The player interaction module manages all in-game actions, such as selecting cards, passing them, and throwing cards to the centre. It also updates the UI to reflect the game's state, displaying each player's cards and their respective points. This module ensures smooth interaction between players, including proper handling of special actions like calling "honors" and tracking the outcomes of such actions.

5. Multiplayer Synchronization Module (Photon)

Photon handles the real-time synchronization of all game actions, ensuring that every player's game state (card positions, player actions, etc.) is kept in sync. This module integrates **Photon** to ensure that actions like passing cards or updating points are reflected across all players' screens in real-time. Photon's network management ensures a seamless multiplayer experience with minimal lag.

5.2. Testing

5.2.1. Test Cases for Unit Testing

Unit testing involves examining individual components of the code in isolation to verify that each unit functions as expected. This process ensures that every part of the system is thoroughly tested for correctness before being integrated into the larger project. In the context of the "**Bray**" card game, unit testing is crucial for verifying the core gameplay mechanics, player interactions, and synchronization in the multiplayer environment.

1. Card Selection and Passing Tests

Test Case 1:

Table 2: Card Selection Test

Case Name:	Card Selection Test
Purpose of Testing:	To verify that a player can select a card correctly.
Expected Result:	A valid card is selected, selected card can be deselected, and no other cards can be selected simultaneously.
Test Steps:	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Simulate a click on a card.2. Check if the card is marked as selected.3. Ensure that no other card is selected at the same time.4. Click on selected card to unselect.
Pass Criteria:	The correct card is selected, and other cards are deselected.
Test Result:	Cards are selected correctly and also selected cards are deselecting.
Comment:	Test successfully passed.

Test Case 2:

Table 3: Card Passing Test

Case Name:	Card Passing Test
Purpose of Testing:	To verify that a player can pass cards to the next player at right hand side.
Expected Result:	The selected cards are passed to the next player, and the hand is updated accordingly.
Test Steps:	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Select 5 cards for passing.2. Wait until all players have selected 5 cards.3. Verify that the 5 cards are removed from the current player's hand and added to the next player's hand.
Pass Criteria:	Cards are passed correctly, and both player hands are updated.
Test Result:	Cards are passing correctly to the right hand player.
Comment:	Test successfully passed.

2. Game State Management Tests

Test Case 3:

Table 4: Round Management Test

Case Name:	Round Management Test
Purpose of Testing:	To verify that the game correctly transitions between rounds.
Expected Result:	After each round, the game progresses to the next round, and the players' points are updated.
Test Steps:	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Play through a round.2. End the round and check if the game state transitions to the next round.3. Ensure points are calculated correctly after each round.
Pass Criteria:	The game progresses to the next round with updated points.
Test Result:	Game is progressing to next round and points are also updating simultaneously.
Comment:	Test successfully passed.

Test Case 4:

Table 5: Points Calculation Text

Case Name:	Points Calculation Test
Purpose of Testing:	To ensure the points are calculated correctly for each player (including honours).
Expected Result:	Players' points should match the rules specified (e.g., 1 point for each heart, 12 points for the Queen of Spades).
Test Steps:	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Simulate a round where players collect hearts and the Queen of Spades2. Check if the points are correctly calculated and displayed.
Pass Criteria:	Points match the expected totals based on the game rules.
Test Result:	Points are matching the expected criteria.
Comment:	Test successfully passed.

3. Photon Networking Tests

Test Case 5:

Table 6: Room Creation Test

Case Name:	Room Creation Test
Purpose of Testing:	To verify that a player can successfully create a new room in Photon
Expected Result:	A new room is created, and the player becomes the host.
Test Steps:	1. Create a new room. 2. Verify the room is created and that the player is listed as the host.
Pass Criteria:	Room is successfully created, and the host is assigned correctly.
Test Result:	Room is created successfully, and the host is assigned Master Player or host.
Comment:	Test successfully passed.

Test Case 6:

Table 7: Room Joining Test

Case Name:	Room Joining Test
Purpose of Testing:	To verify that a player can join an existing room.
Expected Result:	The player should successfully join the room and synchronize with the host.
Test Steps:	1. Create a room and have another player attempt to join. 2. Verify that the second player can join without issues. 3. Check if the game state is synchronized correctly.
Pass Criteria:	Player joins the room, and the game state is synchronized.
Test Result:	Players are joining room without any issues.
Comment:	Test successfully passed, can be add reconnection after disconnection.

4. Player Actions and UI Tests

Test Case 7:

Table 8: UI Update After Card Passing Test

Case Name:	UI Update After Card Passing Test
Purpose of Testing:	To verify that the UI updates after cards are passed.
Expected Result:	The player's hand should update to reflect the cards passed and received.
Test Steps:	1. Pass cards to the next player. 2. Check if the UI updates to reflect the changes in the player's hand.
Pass Criteria:	UI updates correctly and matches the player's hand.
Test Result:	UI updated correctly and each player has 13 cards after exchanging 5 cards.
Comment:	Test successfully passed.

Test Case 8:

Table 9: Card Status Display Test

Case Name:	Game Status Display Test
Purpose of Testing:	To ensure the game status (round, points, player turn) is correctly displayed.
Expected Result:	The UI should show the current round, player points, and the active player turn.
Test Steps:	1. Play a few rounds. 2. Ensure the UI displays correct round, points, and whose turn it is.
Pass Criteria:	The UI updates correctly with game status.
Test Result:	The UI updated correctly and showing right points, round and turn as well vibrating the phones when that player's turn comes.
Comment:	Test successfully passed.

5. Error Handling

Test Case 9:

Table 10: Invalid Card Selection Text

Case Name:	Invalid Card Selection Test
Purpose of Testing:	To test what happens if a player attempts to select more than the allowed number of cards.
Expected Result:	An error should appear, or the extra selection should be ignored.
Test Steps:	1. Attempt to select more than 5 cards for passing. 2. Check if the game properly handles the input.
Pass Criteria:	The game does not allow invalid actions and responds accordingly.
Test Result:	The game doesn't allowing to select more than 5 cards.
Comment:	Test successfully passed.

Test Case 10:

Table 11: Throwing Invalid Card Test

Case Name:	Throwing Invalid Card Test
Purpose of Testing:	To test what happens if a player try to throw illegal card (i.e. Throwing card of another family if it exists).
Expected Result:	An error should appear, or that card can't be thrown.
Test Steps:	1. Attempt to throw illegal card. 2. Check if that card can be thrown.
Pass Criteria:	The game does not allow to throw invalid card.
Test Result:	The game doesn't allowing to throw illegal card until player doesn't have same family card.
Comment:	Test successfully passed.

Test Case 11:

Table 12: Throwing Bray Card Test

Case Name:	Throwing Bray Card Test
Purpose of Testing:	To test is game force to throw the bray card (i.e. Queen Of Spades).
Expected Result:	Game shouldn't allow player to throw another card if bray card required to throw.
Test Steps:	1. Attempt to throw illegal card. 2. Check if that card can be thrown.
Pass Criteria:	The game does not allow to throw another card except bray.
Test Result:	The game doesn't allow to throw illegal card, if requirements met to throw bray.
Comment:	Test successfully passed.

5.3. Result Analysis

The results of testing the "Bray" card game showed that the system effectively provided a smooth and engaging multiplayer experience. Players enjoyed the seamless card passing and game state synchronization, contributing to high levels of user satisfaction. However, some challenges were encountered, such as occasional latency issues and UI difficulties, especially during card selection. These issues occasionally impacted the game's responsiveness and flow. Recommendations for improvement include optimizing network performance to reduce lag, enhancing the user interface for better navigation, and adding more player customization options. Addressing these areas will ensure the game becomes more efficient, enjoyable, and accessible to a broader audience, providing an even more polished experience for future players.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1. Conclusion

The "Online Card Game - Bray" card game project has successfully delivered a dynamic and engaging multiplayer card game experience, using Photon to enable real-time multiplayer functionality. The game's core features, such as card passing, hand management, and player synchronization, have been implemented effectively, providing a seamless experience where players can interact and compete with one another. The system ensures smooth transitions between game states and accurate updates, contributing to a satisfying gameplay environment. Feedback from initial testing has been positive, with players enjoying the game mechanics and the real-time synchronization.

However, some limitations were identified during testing, including occasional latency issues that affected the smoothness of game actions and slight UI navigation difficulties. These challenges, though not significantly disruptive, pointed out areas for further optimization. Ensuring faster network performance and reducing lag will improve gameplay fluidity, particularly during intense rounds. Additionally, enhancing the user interface to make it more intuitive and accessible would increase the overall player experience. Players also suggested adding more customization options to enhance their interaction with the game and improve long-term engagement.

The "Online Card Game - Bray" card game has proven to be a solid foundation for further development. By focusing on network optimization, UI improvements, and additional features, the game can be refined into a highly polished product. With these future updates, "Online Card Game - Bray" has the potential to deliver an even more immersive and enjoyable experience, positioning itself as a standout multiplayer card game suitable for various platforms and audiences.

6.2. Future Recommendations

- Focus on optimizing network performance to minimize latency, ensuring smoother gameplay during multiplayer session.
- Enhancing the user interface for better accessibility and intuitive navigation will improve the overall player experience, especially for new users.
- Implementing additional features such as player customization options, in-game tutorials, and more dynamic game modes can boost long-term engagement.

- Regular bug fixes, performance improvements, and scalability updates are essential to ensure stability, especially when supporting larger player bases.

These enhancements will contribute to a more polished and immersive experience for all players.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. S. Gokhale and A. Traulsen, "Evolutionary multiplayer games," *Dynamic Games and Applications*, vol. 4, pp. 468–488, 2014.
- [2] S. Norozpour and M. Safaei, "An overview on game theory and its application," in *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 993, no. 1. IOP Publishing, 2020, p. 012114.
- [3] M. Kordaki and A. Gousiou, "Digital card games in education: A ten year systematic review," *Computers & Education*, vol. 109, pp. 122–161, 2017.
- [4] "draw.io.," draw io. [Online]. Available: <https://www.draw.io>. [Accessed 11 Dec 2024]
- [5] "PlantUML," PlantUML. [Online]. Available: <http://plantuml.com/>. [Accessed 15 Dec 2024]
- [6] Hayeah, "Playing Cards Assets," *GitHub*. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/hayeah/playing-cards-assets>. [Accessed 10 Oct 2024]

APPENDICES

Figure 16: Initial Screen

Figure 17: Waiting State

Figure 18: Join Room Screen

Figure 19: First Player Screen

Figure 20: Second Player Screen

Figure 21: Third Player Screen

Figure 22: Fourth Player Screen

Figure 23: Card Selection for Passing

Figure 24: After card exchange First player's screen

Figure 25: Card Throwing Turn of Third player

Figure 26: Point displayed at top